

Agricultural Information as a Veritable Tool for Maize Farmers in Ohaji/Egbema Local Government Area of Imo State.

Okoroafor C. K^{1*}, Odocha-Aguocha C. P¹, Mgbemena C. E¹, and Obikee A. C¹.

¹Library Unit, University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Umuagwo, Imo State

*Corresponding author: kingsley.okoroafor@uaes.edu.ng

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Abstract: This paper examines the agricultural information needs of maize farmers in Ohaji/Egbema local government area. Descriptive survey design was used for the study. Data generated were analyzed using simple mean, standard deviation and table. To obtain relevant data and information for study, five research questions and five null hypotheses were formulated based on the research objective to guide this research work. The population of the study is 4500 and the sample size used 450. A questionnaire, focus group discussion and interview were used for data collection. 450 copies of the questionnaire were distributed, while 428 questionnaire were retrieved and used. From the analysis and findings, it was deduced that agricultural information is very importance to maize farmers in Ohaji/ Egbema local government area. It also reveals that the information needs of the people of Ohaji/Egbema are not being met as expected. They are faced with some challenge such as, poor access road to aid the movement of extension workers, agricultural information is not been broadcast with local languages, lack of money to purpose newsletters. However, possible solutions were considered as the best methods to employ in salvaging the said problems eg .government should disseminate agricultural information through to maize farmers media channels(radio and television) twice a week, using the local dialect of the people so as to enable the farmers more especially the illiterate ones comprehend and apply the innovation, and also enforcing that television and radio broadcast on agricultural information is done when most of the farmers would have returned from farm between 7am – 8am, government should deploy extension workers who are familiar with their native language to them.

Keywords: *Agriculture, Information, Maize Farmers, Ohaji/Egbema*

Introduction

Information gap resulting from lack of timely and accurate information

available to individuals and the society at large has altered the level of growth and development of many programs and

most especially, agricultural programs. Hence providing agricultural information to the people of Ohaji-Egbema in Imo State is highly imperative. Information is said to be power. Therefore, the importance of information to the development of agriculture now that the Federal government of Nigeria is doing everything humanly possible to revive the agricultural sector for improved-economy cannot be over emphasized. In agriculture, new information, skill, approach and knowledge will bring about innovation and rapid increase in productivity.

As agriculture becomes more complex, the farmers' access to reliable, timely and relevant information source becomes more critical and demanding. This study will reveal the agricultural information needs of maize farmers in Ohaji-Egbema Local Government Area and the possible ways of providing them with the needed information. By the virtue of this study, poor farm produce will likely to be traced to lack of agricultural information such as; best soil type for planting maize, treatment and control of crop infections, poor application of fertilizers etc.

Unarguably, the human race is totally dependent on agriculture and as the

world population continues to grow, there must be continuous reassessment of agricultural practices to optimize their efficiency (Nwosu, 2021). In many part of the developing countries, agriculture remains a highly efficient industry and continues to demonstrate annual increase in productivity. However, Nigeria is still not sufficient in food production due to many reasons such as lack of good agricultural practice, hostile climate timely or inaccurate information.

The need of agriculture in any economy cannot be overemphasized. It is observed that agriculture is the mainstay of most African economy and occupies a pivotal position in the development of the continent. A nation cannot attain the state of food sufficiency without the development of her farmers. It is therefore imperative that farmers, who are producers of maize should be well informed so they can perform at optimal level. Agriculture is practice for the purpose of producing food, clothing, shelter, medicines and many more. It is also important to note that agriculture is practice as a business for economic gain, growth and development.

Contextually, agriculture can be said to be the art and science of growing plants and other crops and rearing of animals

for food and other human needs or economic gain. According to Rimando (2020), agriculture is the art and science of crop and animal production for human consumption. As a matter of clarification, crop production deals with growing of crops for use as food and fibre. It includes cotton, tobacco, fruits, vegetables, nuts, plants and grains, which maize is one of it.

Maize farming is a very popular form of crop cultivation in Nigeria, and also one of the cereal crops in West Africa. Maize is usually planted in the first quarter of the year. It is an essential diet and is consumed by a number of families. Most homes depend on it as a major source for food. It falls in the family grains. With the right resources and knowledge, one can make a good living out of maize. Maize production plays a vital role in the provision of basic food needs. The evolution of maize planting practice over time had benefitted from skills acquired through cultural/ traditional and scientific methods. This maize farmers comprises of both male and female who are interested in maize farming. Unarguable, this group of persons must have seen maize farming as something lucrative, and that most daily consume foods are from maize. But for them to produce

maximally, information on the application of scientific principle and methods should be made available for them.

It is observed that traditional technique often evolves slowly over several decades, conservatives, limited to a locality or group of people and possible extended by ancestral linkage while the scientific methods has proven to be more versatile, and considered as a better alternative. The application of scientific principles and skills acquire through innovative information has helped to surpass the limitation posed by the traditional way of crop plating, and this has greatly improved production and productivity of grains with the aid of scientific principles (Long, 2015).

Moreover, one of the key ingredient for farmers to yield good maximum output be it subsistence or commercial is information. Agricultural information provision is the major element of advanced agricultural system, as well as essential promoter for agricultural development. Improving provision of agricultural information in rural areas will efficiently fill the information gap presently suffered by the rural farmers with the resulting effect of enhancing agricultural produce.

Information which is so much a part of us, seem to be everywhere at the same time, it is central to all human interactions. It is the basic and one of the earliest activities of human beings. Information has been termed as one of the important of need of man just as food, water, shelter and air Apata and Ogunrewo (2010) described information as an important working tool for the advancement of human and the society at large. Unarguable, any society that does not have access to the pertinent information will sooner or later be left behind in terms of cultural and technological development. Ekoja (2020) opined that information is required for individual growth and development and by extension, social growth and change.

Obviously, there exist a wide gap between the rural and urban dwellers in the areas of physical infrastructure and social amenities. Sadly, this wide difference/gap between the two groups is more pronounced in the present-day Nigeria where the spirit of equality among individuals has not been recognized rather individualism and gross materialism has been the order of the day. The rural farmers have not been recognized as people who need information and most especially timely and accurate information. The relevance

of information in the dissemination of agriculture activities to rural dwellers is indispensable especially at this present dispensation when the Federal Government of Nigeria is making progressive plans towards the development of agricultural sector to better the lives of its citizens and at the same time diversify the economy of the country and create job for the teeming unemployed youth in the country. Information provision to rural dwellers as it concerns improved agricultural produce have been of great worry for rural development especially since the beginning of the economic recession in the country.

According to Oluwatayo and Aliyu (2017), research has shown that maize farmers that are well informed are able to perform better in their production than those that are not well informed and this has led to higher yield and profit. The maize farmers in Ohaji /Egbema LGA need information on possibilities that exist for improving on their lot and how to effect the necessary changes. The people also need specific and detailed information on how to plant maize that will result in an improved of the farm yield or produce.

Agriculture information includes agricultural messages through extension

services embodied in agricultural technologies and shared between the actors in the agricultural extension system (Tadesse, 2019). Agricultural information dissemination is a critical stage of agricultural technology development and transfer. It is critical because if it is not carried out well and through suitable sources, it would not serve the said objectives. Adebayo (2006) asserted that agricultural information is in no doubt imperative in improving agricultural productivity and facilitating poverty alleviation among rural farmers and ensuring all round agriculture and rural development.

There is no doubt in the assertion that agriculture remain the mainstay of the Nigeria economy, employing about 70 to 80% of the population, just as is the case with sub-Sahara Africa countries. But unfortunately, Sub- Sahara Africa (SSA) stands out as the only region where overall poverty and food insecurity continue to worsen (Forum for Agriculture Research in Africa, 2006) This trend does not signify a good economic performance to the region especially in Nigeria. For the simple fact that the agricultural growth rate was low than the population growth rate is the main concern regarding the performance of the sector. In the light of the above,

Nwodo (2017) asserts that Nigeria has grim economic outlook. Nigeria's external debt has grown unexpectedly, so there is no doubt that the time has come for us to retrace our steps back to agriculture.

Statement of the problem

The gap between the rural and urban dwellers in the area of agriculture information has been observed by many. Sadly, this gap between the two groups is more evident in the present-day Nigeria where the spirit of equality among individuals has not been recognized rather individualism and gross materialism has been the order of the day. Adequate agricultural information is vital for optimal crop productivity. The rural farmers more especially maize farmers in Ohaji/Egbema LGA have not been recognized as people who need timely and accurate information and as a result, it has affected their farm yield. The relevance of information in the dissemination of agriculture activities to rural farmers in Ohaji/Egbema is indispensable especially at this present dispensation when the Federal Government of Nigeria is making progressive plans towards the development of agricultural sector to better the lives of its citizens and at the same time diversify the

economy of the country and create job for the teaming unemployed youth in the country. However, the observed want of information provision services to farmers in Ohaji/Egbema in particular have been of great concern due to the insufficient food production especially since the beginning of the economic recession in the country.

Purpose of the Study

The general purpose of this study is to investigate the effectiveness of the provision of agricultural information needs in enhancing the productivity of maize farmers in Ohaji/Egbema Local Government Area.

The following specific objectives will guide the study:

1. To determine the agricultural information needs of maize farmers in Ohaji/Egbema LGA
2. To find out the source through which maize farmers in Ohaji/Egbema LGA access information.
3. To ascertain the extent to which the information needs of maize farmers in Ohaji/Egbema LGA area are met.
4. To find out the problems faced by the maize farmers in Ohaji/Egbema LGA when accessing information

5. To determine strategies for improving information provision for maize farmers in Ohaji/Egbema LGA

Research Questions

1. What are the agricultural information needs of maize farmers in Ohaji/Egbema LGA?
2. What are the source through which maize farmers in Ohaji/Egbema LGA access information?
3. To what extent are the agricultural information needs of maize farmers in Ohaji/Egbema LGA area met?
4. What are the problems faced by the maize farmers in Ohaji/Egbema LGA when accessing information?
5. What strategies could be employed in improving agricultural information provision for maize farmers in Ohaji/Egbema LGA?

Hypotheses

The following hypothetical statement are formulated for this study.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean rating of male and female maize farmers on their information needs.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the mean rating of male and female maize farmers on the sources through which they access information.

H₀₃: There is no significant difference between the mean rating of the male and female maize farmers on the extent to which their information needs are met.

H₀₄: There is no significant difference between the mean rating of male and female maize farmers on the problems faced when accessing information.

H₀₅: There is no significant difference between the mean rating of male and female maize farmers on the strategies for improving information provision.

Significance of the Study

The findings of this study will be useful to the following group of people; the maize farmers, policy makers (government) and researchers.

The result of this study will be of great benefit to the maize farmers in Ohaji/Egbema Local Government Area, Imo State and to Nigeria farmers in general. Maize Farmers will be enlightened on the innovative improvements in agriculture and as well stand the chance of competing

favourably with their counterpart in the world.

The finding will be useful to policy makers / government, for it will expose the need for proper implementation and continuous monitoring of their policies. This will also make the government know the need of involving the farmers in policy making and not making policies without being abreast of the farmers information needs.

The finding of this study will also serve as empirical base for future researchers who may wish to carry out further research on farmers information needs or in related topic.

Literature Review

Concept of information

Information is the life wire of any society. The relevance of information to farmers increase by the day. It is information that satisfies the individual desire to know or acquire knowledge on existing subject or field. Odunewo and Omagbemi (2008) also asserted that information is one of the basic human needs after air, water, food and shelter. This makes information very fundamental to every living of people all over the world thereby, enabling people

to relate with one another. The concept information also refers to the facts obtained from various sources or media use in reshaping the vision, thoughts, understanding and actions of individuals or group (Kolawole and Igwe, 2021). According to Okezie (2015) information is naturally in abundance in various formats and various sources with intrinsic value. It has the ability to alter positions, views, persons, situations, as well as mind-set. When people require information to solve certain problems, the issue of information needs arises. However, information that is not accessible is information that is not useable. This underpins the perspective of United Nation Development Programme (UNDP), as cited in Amadi, Udo and Ekpenyoung (2020), which posit that information that is available and useful is that information that is accessible. Farmers in Ohaji-Egbema needs information, because the steady flow of information, whether through digital tools or manual systems keeps human society alive, and serves as a prime agent for actions and societal transformation

Agricultural information need of maize farmers

One of the key ingredients for farmers to yield good output is information.

Information such as weather forecast, types of soil and the best soil type for planting different maize, better crop rotation practice and fertilizer application, crop disease treatment and control, agricultural credit facilities, improved varieties of seeds e.t.c. Information need is the lack of appropriate information on which to base choice for better service or benefit in general. Information need, as Miranda and Tarapanof (2008) put it, is defined as a state or process started when one perceived that there is a gap between the information and knowledge available to solve a problem and the actual solution to the problem. In LisWiki (Library and information science Wiki) (2008), information need seen as the recognition that one's knowledge is inadequate to satisfy a goal.

Information Provision of Improved tools and equipment

Farming is much slower and less productive due to the unavailability of information on new and improved technology to the farmers. As of today, majority of the farmers still make use of crude tools such as hoes, cutlasses etc. all these make agricultural production less timely and slow and consequently low yield. The uses of modern tools have been confirmed by many authors to

be timely and more effective in agricultural production. Information and use of improved technologies tend to raise output level and reduce average cost of production which in turn results in substantial gains in farm income (Challa, 2023).

Information on Soil type

Some crops, e.g maize require certain soil conditions for productivity. Example soil that is good for groundnut may not be good for maize. Information should be given to this farmers to improve the conditions of the soil and the type of soil meant for a particular seed or plant. One way of doing this is by educating the farmers on the applications of organic and sometimes inorganic fertilizers. A number of authors have reported increased yield following the application of fertilizers in nutrient low soils (Amanze *et al.*, 2022).

Information on the use of improved crop varieties, fertilizers, pesticides and so on

Farmers should be familiar with the benefit of improved crop varieties and chemical fertilizers through exposures and these inputs should be easily accessible through cooperative societies. The importance of the use of improved crop varieties and other inputs cannot be overemphasized. Take for instance a

linear endogenous treatment–effect model based on a matched sample obtained from propensity score matching shows that improved maize varieties increase maize yields by 38.7%. At the same time, the selectivity-corrected and stochastic metafrontier approaches show that the yield advantage of improved varieties results from their high technology (Olasehinde *et al.*, 2023). The information on varieties and agrochemicals should be disseminated and distributed cheaply throughout the rural communities.

Agricultural Information Sources

The government should take more action in informing the people on the sources through which maize farmers can access agricultural information. Due to the need to access available information by farmers who have the potential to promote agricultural productivity, maize farmers should be exposed to all sources available e.g radio, television, community library, extension exhibition (Agbato, 2008, Fahimuddin *et al.*, 2016). Sources of pertinent information as one of the factor of production is very relevant in agricultural production. Unarguable, the quality and quantity of information and its sources goes a long way in education farmers on what is expected of them.

Maize farmers experience massive failure in agricultural production due to information on the crop they are producing and other related factors affecting their production. Any attempt in mastering this interrelated factors will definitely affect their yields. The right sources to know about a crop, when to apply fertilizer and/or pesticides, mode of storage to mention but a few will go a long way in increasing farmers yields (Agbato, 2008).

It is therefore important that farmers access information through information sources readily available for them, for this will keep the farmers abreast of timely information and as such contribute to food security and economic growth. The maize farmers in Ohaji-Egbema requires information in the supply of inputs, new technology, early warning systems on drought, pest and diseases, credit, market prices and their favourable competitors so as to actively and effectively contribute to national economic growth and agricultural development. Many studies have shown that the information provisions as regards the use of improved farm inputs such as high yielding crop varieties, improved farm tools and equipment has tremendously increased crop yields (Challa, 2023).

Empirical Study

Eze (2013) conducted a research on the information needs of prison and resource provision through the prison library in south- East zone of Nigeria. The research design used was descriptive survey. In a similar view, Ozioko (2007) studied the reproductive health information need of rural women in Enugu State. Survey research technique was used as well. In the same view, Ekoja (2004) carried out a study on sensitizing users for increased information use; the case of Nigerian farmers. The study also adopted descriptive survey. The above related works were similar with the present work as it relates to information and the research design adopted. But differs in topic and area of study (farmers in Ohaji-Egbema LGA). This is the gap in literature the researcher intends to fill.

However, access to pertinent and timely information could be militated by certain factors such as poverty, lack of technological equipment, cost, inconsistency of extension workers, lack of community libraries and its expected information materials, etc. It is in this backdrop therefore, that this study attempt to find out the information needs of maize farmers and the provision of these information to

The people of Ohaji /Egbema.

Methodology

Area of Study

The study will be carried out in Ohaji-Egbema Local Government Area of Imo State. Ohaji-Egbema is an oil-rich Local Government Area in the Imo State Nigeria. The local council lies in the south-western part of Imo state with land area of 1,154,4,6 square kilometers. It shares boundaries with Owerri in the East, Oguta LGA in the north and Ogba/Egbema/Ndomi in Rivers state in the South-West. Its headquarters is Mmahu-Egbema. The local government area was created by the Gen. Ibrahim B. Babangida's administration by the August 27, 1991 presidential proclamation, created out of the former Ohaji/Egbema/Oguta LGA. Ohaji/Egbema comprises of three political district: Ohaji East, Egbema North, and Ohaji West. The Ohaji/Egbema Local Government Area has seventeen autonomous communities. The inhabitants of these communities are predominantly petty traders, subsistence farmers and civil servants. Their economic activities are based on agricultural work, including the cultivation of cassava, potatoes, corn, yam, etc.

Research Design:

Survey research design was used for the study. Survey is a research method which focuses on a representative sample derived from the entire population (Nwodu, 2006). This method is pertinent because of its ability to ensure a representative outlook and provide a simple approach to the study of values, opinion and attitude of people. It as well provides researchers the opportunity to have a face to face interaction with the respondents.

Population of the Study

The population of the study is made up of all the registered crop farmers' cooperative societies in the Ohaji/Egbema LGA. According to the data obtained from the ministry of Agriculture and Natural Resources Imo (2023) the population of the registered members of maize farmers' cooperative societies in Ohaji/Egbema LGA area is 4500 farmers.

Sampling Techniques and Sample Size

Sample size for this study would be 10% of the population (450). This 10% sample size will be randomly selected using simple random sampling technique. To ascertain this, the researcher will number, fold and put the

names of this farmers in a container which will be well-shaken before randomly picking the respondents without replacement. This procedure will be used to avoid bias.

Instrument for Data Collection

The Instrument for data collection were questionnaire, focus group discussion and interview for eliciting more information from both the literate and non- literate respondents. Seventeen (5) Research assistance were used for data collection; each for a particular town so as to ensure accuracy and efficiency. The questionnaire was used to collect quantitative data while the focused group discussion and interview instrument was used to collect qualitative data for the study.

Data Analysis

The data generated from the questionnaire were collated, presented and analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions. The calculated mean score was computed using the following formula below.

$$\bar{X} = \sum \frac{FX}{N}$$

Where \bar{X} = Mean

Σ = Summation

F = Frequency

X = Score

N = No of scores

The weight of the response options of the questionnaire items thus:

SA/VH = 4

A/H = 3

D/LE = 2

SD/VLE = 1

The criterion mean is to be computed using four (4) Likert Scale

$$\frac{4+3+2+1}{4} = \frac{10}{4} = 2.5$$

Strongly Agree/very High Extent = 3.50-4.00

Agree/High Extent = 2.50-3.499

Low extent/Disagree = 1.50-2.499

Very low extent/ strongly disagree = 1.00-1.99

However, a mean of 2.50 was adopted as a decision rule for the analysis of the data collected. An item with the mean of 2.50 and above was regarded as greed to/high extent while item below 2.50 were regarded as being to a low extent/Disagree to question while the calculated mean scores were gotten using the raw data generated using SPSS(statistical package of the social

sciences) . The null hypotheses and not significant if the calculated t-test postulated for the study were tested for is equal or greater than value at 0.05 significance using t-test statistics at 0.05 level of significance. level of significant. Thus, the null hypothesis was significant if the calculated t-test was less than the t-table,

Results and Discussion of Findings

Table 1 Agricultural information needs of the maize farmers in Ohaji-Egbema local government area

S/N	Items	Literate Farmers			Non-Literate Farmers		
		X	SD	Decision	X	SD	Decision
1	Introduction of new pesticides and herbicides/uses	3.50	0.45	SA	3.58	0.37	SA
2	Better crop(maize) rotation practices and application of fertilizers	3.63	0.39	SA	3.76	0.54	A
3	Soil type and the best soil type for planting maize	3.59	0.42	SA	3.89	0.33	SA
4	Introduction of improved maize seedlings	2.56	0.98	A	2.89	0.79	A
5	Crop disease treatment and control	2.58	0.67	A	2.59	0.93	A
6	Use of artificial planting method	2.94	0.52	A	3.16	0.84	A
7	New methods of maize preservation	2.90	0.77	A	2.67	0.69	A
	Grand Mean/SD	3.1	0.6	A	3.22	0.64	A

Table 1 shows that the mean score for literate maize farmers range from 2.56 to 3.63 with a grand mean of 3.1 and a standard deviation of 0.60. The grand mean of 3.10 shows that maize farmers in Ohaji/Egbema agreed to a high extent that they are in need of agricultural information as itemized. The mean score of the non-literate farmers range from 2.59 to 3.89 with a grand mean of 3.22 and standard of 0.64. This grand mean of 3.22 also shows that non-literate farmers agree to a high extent that agricultural information is necessary. It

simply denotes that the both group of farmers agreed to various information needs as itemized above. Though introduction of new herbicides and pesticides/use and type of soil and the best soil type for planting were rank highest with a mean score of 3.50, 3.59 and 3.58, 3.89 respectively. The findings show that agricultural information such as soil type, introduction of new herbicides, use of artificial planting methods etc are very useful for promoting agricultural productivity. This study is in line with

(Challa, 2023) who started that Information and use of improved technologies tend to raise output level and reduce average cost of production which in turn results in substantial gains in farm income . This study is also in

line with Amanze et al(2023) who asserted that introduction of new herbicide and the best soil type planting are agricultural information needed by rural farmers for optimal crop productivity.

Table 2 Sources through which maize farmers in Ohaji/Egbema Local Government Area are more likely to access agricultural information

S/N	Items	Literate Farmers			Non-Literate Farmers		
		X	SD	Decision	X	SD	Decision
1	Community library	2.44	0.54	D	2.33	0.66	D
2	Newsletters	2.59	0.65	D	1.89	0.55	D
3	Families and friends	3.58	0.43	SA	3.96	0.45	SA
4	Exhibitions	2.32	0.12	D	2.18	0.12	D
5	Town criers	2.47	0.96	D	2.35	0.45	D
6	Radio	3.50	0.34	SA	3.56	0.14	SA
7	Television	3.57	0.68	SA	2.54	0.75	SA
8	Extension workers	2.53	0.54	D	2.59	0.44	D
	Grand Mean/SD	2.87	0.53	A	2.67	0.44	A

Table 2 Shows that the mean score for literate maize farmers range from 2.23 to 3.58 with a grand mean of 2.87 and a standard deviation of 0.53. The grand mean of 2.87 shows that literate maize farmers in Ohaji/Egbema agreed that they use the information sources itemized in accessing agricultural information. The mean score of the non-literate maize farmers range from 1.89 to 3.96 with a grand mean of 2.67 and standard deviation of 0.44. This grand mean of 2.67 also shows that non-literate maize farmers agree to the sources itemize in accessing agricultural information. It simply denotes that the

both group of farmers agreed to various information sources itemized above. Though families and friends, radio and television were rank highest with a mean score of 3.50 and above respectively. The group discussion and interview conduct reveals the same information with the data gotten from the questionnaires distributed. The findings show that agricultural information are easily accessed through families and friends with the mean score of 3.58 and 3.96 respectively. This work is in line with Ekoja (2020) who state that farmers seek agricultural information more from families, friend and radio. It is also in

line with Challa (2023) who opined that farmers prefers to seek agricultural information from families and friends

because they feel more comfortable with them.

Table 3 Information needs of the maize farmers in Ohaji/Egbema Local Government Area met

S/N	Items	Literate Farmers			Non-Literate Farmers		
		X	SD	Decision	X	SD	Decision
1	Introduction of new pesticides and herbicides/uses	2.11	0.44	LE	2.18	0.33	LE
2	Better crop rotation practices and fertilizer application	2.25	0.67	LE	2.44	0.29	LE
3	Types of soil and the best soil type for planting	2.54	0.45	HE	2.17	0.43	LE
4	Introduction of improved seedlings	2.49	0.21	HE	2.00	0.22	LE
5	Crop disease treatment and control	2.54	0.19	HE	2.26	0.23	LE
6	Use of mechanised planting methods	2.33	0.43	LE	2.01	0.62	LE
7	New methods of crop preservation	2.48	0.59	LE	2.10	0.74	LE
	Grand Mean/SD	2.39	0.42	LE	2.16	0.41	LE

Table 3. Shows that the mean score for literate farmers range from 2.11 to 2.54 with a grand mean of 2.39 and a standard deviation of 0.42. The grand mean of 2.39 shows that literate maize farmers in Ohaji/Egbema disagree and well responded to a low extent that their agricultural information needs are not met as itemized above. The mean score of the non-literate farmers range from 2.01 to 2.44 with a grand mean of 2.16 and standard of 0.41. This grand mean of 2.16 also shows that non-literate maize farmers disagree and responded to a low extent that their agricultural information needs are not met. It simply denotes that the both group of farmers

responded that their information needs are not met as itemised above. Though the literate maize farmers responded positively to type of soil and the best soil type for planting and crop disease treatment and control with a mean score of 2.54 and 2.54. The interview and discussions carried out were in line with the responses gotten from the findings above. This work is in line with Ekpenyoung (2020), who posit that information that is available and useful is that information that is accessible. This work is in agreement with Okezie (2015) also stated that information not passed is as good as no information.

Table 4 Problems faced by the maize farmers in Ohaji/Egbema Local Government Area in the course of accessing agricultural information

S/N	Items	Literate Farmers			Non-Literate Farmers		
		X	SD	Decision	X	SD	Decision
1	Extension workers lack good public relation	3.54	0.65	A	3.65	0.27	A
2	Inability to read and write i.e. illiteracy	2.47	0.32	D	3.82	0.81	SA
3	Television and radio signals are very poor	2.11	0.41	D	2.34	0.53	D
4	Agricultural information on radio and television is always aired at odd hours when farmers who desire such information have gone to their farms	3.89	0.51	SA	3.86	0.36	SA
5	Lack of rural electrification or constant epileptic power supply in communities that have electricity	3.90	0.59	SA	3.54	0.31	SA
6	Lack of access roads for easy community visit of extension workers	3.50	0.54	A	2.64	0.54	A
7	Agricultural information on maize planting is not broadcast on radio and television using the native language	3.98	0.65	SA	3.59	0.44	SA
8	Insufficient fund to purchase newsletters, leaflets on agricultural information	2.23	0.32	D	2.11	0.72	D
	Grand Mean/SD	3.16	0.49	A	3.19	0.49	A

Table 4 Shows that the mean score for literate maize farmers range from 2.11 to 3.89 with a grand mean of 3.16 and a standard deviation of 0.49. The grand mean of 3.16 shows that literate maize farmers in Ohaji/Egbema agreed to the problems faced in the course of accessing agricultural information as itemised above. The mean score of the non-literate maize farmers range from 2.11 to 3.82 with a grand mean of 3.19 and standard deviation of 0.49. This grand mean of 3.19 also shows that non-literate maize farmers agree to the problems faced in the course of accessing agricultural information as itemized. It simply denotes that both group of farmers agreed that they face

problems in accessing agricultural information. Though the literate and non-literate maize farmers responded positively that agricultural information is not broadcast on radio and television using the native language, Agricultural information on radio and television is always aired at odd hours when farmers who desire such information have gone to their farms. However, they disagree on the inability to read and right with a mean score of 2.47 and 3.82 respectively. The group discussion and interview are in agreement with the findings above. This is in line with the findings of Oluwatayo and Aliyu (2007) which found that maize farmers that are well informed through means suitable for

them are able to perform better in their production than those that are not well informed and this has led to higher yield and profit. The maize farmers need information on possibilities that exist for improving on their lot and how to effect the necessary changes. This work is also

in line with Olasehinde (2023) who state that farmers in rural communities are faced a lot of problems like lack of radio and television antenna signals, inexperience extension workers being sent to rural communities.

Table 5 Strategies for improving information provision for the rural farmers in Ohaji/Egbema Local Government Area

S/N	Items	Literate Farmers			Non-Literate Farmers		
		X	SD	Decision	X	SD	Decision
1	Construction of access roads with enduring value that would aid regular visits of extension workers and other agricultural agents	3.53	0.53	SA	3.65	0.32	SA
2	Establishment of libraries in various communities that would facilitate the procurement of , newsletters, books, leaflets, magazines etc. on agricultural information	2.57	0.85	A	2.17	0.75	D
3	Installation of community rural electrification by government	3.66	0.52	SA	3.51	0.45	SA
4	Provision of more power transformers to limit power interruptions	2.50	0.63	A	2.77	0.62	A
5	Radio and television stations in the state should install antennas to aid in better reception of radio and television signals	2.89	0.91	A	2.91	0.78	A
6	Agricultural information should be disseminated on radio and television twice a week, using Ohaji/Egbema dialect to enable the illiterate farmers comprehend and apply the innovations	3.00	0.34	A	3.97	0.49	SA
7	Ensuring that radio broadcast on agricultural information is done when most of the rural farmers would have returned from farm (7 and 8pm)	3.54	0.39	SA	3.85	0.86	SA
	Grand Mean/SD	3.09	0.66	A	3.26	0.61	A

Table 5 shows that the mean score for literate maize farmers range from 2.50 to 3.66 with a grand mean of 3.09 and a standard deviation of 0.66. The grand mean of 3.09 shows that literate maize farmers in Ohaji/Egbema agreed to the strategies for improving information provision to maize farmers. The mean score of the non-literate maize farmers

range from 2.17 to 3.97 with a grand mean of 3.26 and standard deviation of 0.61. This grand mean of 3.26 also shows that non-literate maize farmers agree to the strategies for improving information provision to maize farmers. It simply denotes that the both group of farmers agreed to the strategies as itemized above. Though the literate and

non-literate maize farmers responded positively to ensuring that radio broadcast on agricultural information is done when majority of the rural farmers would have returned from farm(7and 8pm) . This work is in line with the submission of challa (2023). It stated that radio broadcast is readily accessible to farmer in the rural community and that agricultural information should be

passed via the radio. The work of Amanze (2023) is also in line with the current work.It stated that agricultural information should be broadcast when the farmers must have been back from the farm.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean rating of male and female maize farmers on their agricultural information needs.

Table 6 T-test of significant difference between the mean rating of male and female maize farmers on their agricultural information need

Farmers	N	Mean	Std	df	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Male	230	2.17	0.40	190	0.29	1.96	Not significant
Female	198	2.82	0.54	190			

Table 6 shows that t-cal of 0.29 is less than t-crit of 1.96 at 0.05 alpha level of significance with 190 degree of freedom. This means there is no significance difference between the mean responses of male and female maize farmers on

their agricultural information need. The null hypothesis is, therefore, not rejected.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the mean rating of male and female maize farmers on the sources to which they access agricultural information.

Table 7 T-test of significant difference between the mean rating of male and female maize farmers on the sources to which they access agricultural information

Farmers	N	Mean	Std	df	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Male	230	2.43	0.33	190	0.54	1.96	Not significant
Female	198	2.27	0.34	190			

Table 7 shows that t-cal of 0.54 is less than t-crit of 1.96 at 0.05 alpha level of significance with 190 degree of freedom. This means there is no significance difference between the mean responses of male and female maize farmers on the sources through which they access

agricultural information. The null hypothesis is, therefore, not rejected.

H₀₃: There is no significant difference between the mean rating of male and female maize farmers on the extent to which their agricultural information needs are met.

Table 8 T-test of significant difference between the mean rating of male and female maize farmers on the extent to which their agricultural information needs are met

Farmers	N	Mean	Std	df	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Male	230	2.29	0.82	190	0.46	1.96	Not significant
Female	198	2.15	0.51	190			

Table 8 shows that t-cal of 0.46 is less than t-crit of 1.96 at 0.05 alpha level of significance with 190 degree of freedom. This means there is no significance difference between the mean responses of the male and female maize farmers on the extent to which their agricultural

information needs are met. The null hypothesis is, therefore, not rejected.

H₀₄: There is no significant difference between the mean rating of male and Female maize farmers on the problems face in the course of accessing agricultural information.

Table 9 T-test of significant difference between the mean rating of male and female maize farmers on the problems face in the course of accessing agricultural information

Farmers	N	Mean	Std	df	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Male	230	3.26	0.59	190	0.87	1.96	Not Significant
Female	198	3.15	0.49	190			

Table 9 shows that t-cal of 0.87 is less than t-crit of 1.96 at 0.05 alpha level of

significance with 190 degree of freedom. This means there is no significance

difference between the mean responses of male and female maize farmers on the problems face in the course of accessing agricultural information. The null hypothesis is, therefore, not rejected.

H₀₅: There is no significant difference between the mean rating of male and female maize farmers on the strategies for improving the provision of agricultural information to crop farmers.

Table 10 T-test of significant difference between the mean rating of the male and female maize farmers on the strategies for improving the provision of Agricultural information to maize farmers

Farmers	N	Mean	Std	df	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Male	230	3.09	0.49	190	0.96	1.96	Not significant
Female	198	3.26	0.61	190			

Table 10 shows that t-cal of 0.96 is less than t-crit of 1.96 at 0.05 alpha level of significance with 190 degree of freedom. This means there is no significance difference between the mean responses of male and female maize farmers on the strategies for improving the profession of agricultural information. The null hypothesis is, therefore, not rejected.

Conclusion:

The agricultural information needs of maize farmers in Ohaji/Egbema local government area cut across the type of soil to plant, better crop rotation, fertilization application, introduction to new seedling. For the famers to perform maximally, these information needs must be attended to without delay. It was noticed that the maize farmers

prefer some communication channels through which they access agricultural information to others. The maize farmers prefers to access this agricultural information through families, friends and radio, and more especially in their local languages, and preferable between the hours of 7pm-8pm when they must have been back from their various farms. The farmer also collectively agreed that the services of extension workers are not been felt as expected in the communities that made up Ohaji/Egbema. Some challenges like bad road which has hindered the services of the extension workers from reaching the rural maize farmers; inadequate radio and television station antennas for better signals; and poor electrification were identified as major challenges faced by the farmers. The

farmers also suggested the installation of community rural electrification by the government; good road and radio or television station antennas as possible strategies in providing agricultural information to maize farmers in Ohaji/Egbema LGA.

Recommendations

1. The Government should Ensure that the people of Ohaji/Egbema get the required agricultural information on best soil type for planting, method for disease control, application of fertilizers through trained extension workers information
2. The government should ensure that rural community electrification and radio/ television station antennas are made available for effective broadcast of agricultural information and more especially when majority of the maize farmers would have returned from farm between 7pm – 8pm
3. The government should ensure that Extension workers are deployed to the various communities that made up Ohaji/ Egbema LGA so as to educate and inform the people of the necessary agricultural information

4. The government should deploy to the area extension workers whom are good in public relation and as well familiar with the local dialect of Ohaji/Egbema.
5. Government should disseminate agricultural information to maize farmers on radio and television twice a week, using Ohaji/Egbema dialect to enable the illiterate farmers understand and apply the innovation
6. Government should at intervals organize agricultural seminars for farmers more especially maize farmers in Ohaji/Egbema LGA
7. The government should see to the construction of good roads that would aid effectively and timely agricultural information delivery.

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